

Physicochemical Parameters Assessment of Agricultural Soils around Auto-Mechanic Workshops in Ohaji/Egbema, Imo State: Soil, Health Implications, and Sustainability

Okoro N. J¹., Eze V. C^{1*}., Ononogbo C²., Emeagubor A. O¹., Egbucha J. N¹., Eberendu K. O¹., Nlemchukwu B. N. C¹.

¹Department of Chemistry, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: ezevictor54@yahoo.com

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Abstract: The analysis showed different concentrations of physico-chemical parameters and PAHs in agricultural soil samples around auto-mechanic workshops in three different communities, namely, Abacheke, Mmahu, and Obokofia (sample A, sample B, and sample C, respectively), in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area, Imo State. In another community, with no visible evidence of auto-mechanic activities or contamination of soil, a control sample was collected. Topsoil samples were collected at a depth of 0-10 cm using a soil auger in ten (10) locations per community which formed a sample representative of the respective communities giving a total of thirty sub-samples and one control sample for this study. PAH analysis was done using Dichloromethane (DCM) (to extract PAHs from the soil samples), Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS) Shimadzu Model 2010 with an HP-5MS fused silica column, while selective ion monitoring (SIM) mode was used to collect the data. The mean values of pH, temperature, electrical conductivity, and total petroleum hydrocarbon are within the ranges of 3.99 ± 0.24 – 4.83 ± 0.37 , $28.54 \pm 0.02^\circ\text{C}$ – $32.68 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$, $230.57 \pm 41.32 \mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$ – $295.31 \pm 26.01 \mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$ and $947.61 \pm 35.08 \text{ mg/kg}$ – $1586.24 \pm 78.93 \text{ mg/kg}$, respectively, throughout the sample locations. The total PAHs concentration (mg/kg) is within the range of 18.7464 - 19.8505 in the sample locations, greater than 0.0095 mg/kg found in the control sample. The 2–3 ring low molecular weight (LMW) of the total concentrations of PAHs ranging from 9.2446 - 10.1917 in all sampling locations were significantly above the 4–6 ring high molecular weight (HMW) PAHs ranging from 2.355 to 2.8528 in all sampling locations. This study has revealed that agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops in Abacheke, Mmahu, and Obokofia in Ohaji/Egbema, are acidic (low pH) with high total petroleum hydrocarbon value while, the electrical conductivity are lower than the recommended limit according to the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). Phenanthrene, Anthracene and Flourene were predominant in the three communities, while both *Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene and *Benzo[g,h,i]perylene showed the least. The high values of PAHs reported is an indication that the auto-mechanic workshop soils are highly contaminated and hence are detrimental to human health as a result of anthropogenic activities on the soil. The findings recommend proper siting of auto-mechanic workshops far away from agricultural soils, education and adequate training for auto-mechanic workers, and subsequent collection and recycling of spent oils, which will in turn provide employment opportunities and provide revenue for the government.

Keyword: Physicochemical parameters, PAH, soil, auto-mechanic, Ohaji/Egbema.

Introduction

Agricultural soils are heavily exposed to contamination by toxic substances as a result of industrialization and anthropogenic activities, with negative effects on human health and the ecosystem (Amos *et al.*, 2023). Agriculture has been important to human beings for many years, as human beings rely on agriculture for their entire needs in life. These include provision of foods, clothing materials, employment, income, foreign exchange, a market for industrial goods, shelter, medicinal herbs, tourist attractions, and raw materials. The roles of agriculture in the national economy include provision of employment, revenue, basic amenities, and foreign exchange (Nwogwugwu *et al.*, 2023). Studies revealed that crop and livestock production have significant impacts on the economic growth in Nigeria (Chukwu and Benjamin, 2023). Therefore, the ever-increasing human population of Nigeria means more food is needed to feed the people, while the surplus is sold to generate income, thereby improving the quantity and quality of food produced through food safety and security.

The soil is essential to all living things as it supports habitat for organisms and helps to dissolve plant nutrients. Plants derive water and nutrients from the soil in order to produce

a greater yield during harvest. However, the quality of soil has deteriorated as a result of human activities, which have led to environmental problem. Agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops are contaminated by harmful substances that are released into the environment by the auto-mechanics without consideration for hazardous environmental effects, as some of them are not trained formally (Sharifi *et al.*, 2007; Utibe *et al.*, 2020). The wastes produced and disposed of into the environment by auto-mechanic repair shops are of major concern as they are absorbed into the soil, reducing the quantity and quality of food produced and, hence, the national economy (Timothy *et al.*, 2023a).

As a result of the increase in urbanization, there is an increase in the use of vehicles as a means of transportation. Studies have shown that vehicular activities in the cities are responsible for more potential carcinogen exposure than the industrial zone. Cancer risks for soil-bound carcinogenic PAHs resulting from transportation activities were found to be two to three times higher than those obtained from industrial processes (Debananda *et al.*, 2022). Often times, the use of vehicles requires maintenance to prolong the lifespan of vehicles, and most of the time, human activities such as accidental releases

and careless disposal practices are sources of petroleum-based products (Duru *et al.*, 2017; Nkwoada and Amakom, 2018; Duru *et al.*, 2019; Ibe *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, auto-mechanic waste dump sites are known to have high concentration levels of petroleum hydrocarbons. These persistent organic pollutants (POPs), such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins, etc., are introduced into the soil, causing great harm (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2008; Utibe *et al.*, 2020). Also, the sale of automobile spare parts and engine oil, as well as servicing and repair of various car parts, which usually involves spraying or painting, soldering, battery recharging, welding, are conducted in these auto-mechanic workshops, which may contain heavy metals and PAHs (Adelekan and Abegunde, 2011; Obini *et al.*, 2013; Owoso *et al.*, 2017; Amukali *et al.*, 2018; Timothy *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, the spills from petroleum-based products such as lubricants, gasoline, diesel, and by-products of used and spent engine oil constitute the major pollutants in the soil in auto-mechanic villages (Adelana and Adeosun, 2011). These petroleum-based products eventually get absorbed by the soil and subsequently by the food crops, thereby resulting in high levels of PAHs. This in turn impacts negatively on the

food chain on exposure to the human body, directly or indirectly when consumed (Abhulimhen *et al.*, 2016; Mackiewicz-walec *et al.*, 2020; Utibe *et al.*, 2020; Edna *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, a significant concentration of PAH in the soil can affect food safety (Tengfei *et al.*, 2024).

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are persistent organic pollutants that are resistant to biological degradation with many fused aromatic rings and are known to be found everywhere across the globe, which causes serious harm to plants, animals, and humans (Obini *et al.*, 2013; Ololade, 2014). It can be found naturally from volcanic eruptions, wildfires, fossil fuel deposits such as coal, and in petroleum. However, in urban or industrial areas, soil contamination by polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) is most often caused by human activity, release, and indiscriminate dumping of wastes in auto-mechanic workshops and industrial production activities, such as the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, etc., which increase the risk of cancer (Peng *et al.*, 2021). It can also affect some organs, such as the skin, pancreas, colon, etc. (Manthar *et al.*, 2022; Tarkan *et al.*, 2022). The United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2011) has recognized sixteen (16) PAHs as prevalent and persistent based on their

negative effects on humans and animals. The carcinogenic PAHs include Indeno(1,2,3-cd)perylene (IndP), Chrysene(Chry), Benzo(a)pyrene(BaP), Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene (DahA), Benzo(a)anthracene(BaA), Benzo(b)fluoranthene (BbF), and benzo(k)fluoranthene (BkF) while the non-carcinogenic PAHs include Pyrene (Pyr), Phenanthrene (Phe), Naphthalene (Nap), Fluorene (Flu), Anthracene (Ant), Fluoranthene (Flt), Acenaphthylene (Acy), Acenaphthene (Ace), and Benzo(ghi)perylene (BghiP) (Timothy *et al.*, 2023b; Eze *et al.*, 2024). The 16 PAHs are generally divided into two groups based on their ring number (Chen *et al.*, 2019). 2-3 ring PAHs are referred to as low-molecular-weight (LMW), while 5-6 ring are high-molecular-weight (HMW). Light PAHs (LPAHs, i.e., 2- and 3-rings) are abundant in petrogenic sources, while high molecular PAHs (HPAHs, i.e., 4-, 5-, and 6-rings) are indicative of pyrogenic origin (Budzinski *et al.*, 1997). In general, HMW-PAHs concentrations are higher than MMW-PAHs or LMW-PAHs because of their low volatility, stability, and high resistance to degradation, and thus accumulation in soils, whereas LMW-PAHs are unstable (Mu *et al.*, 2017; Lee and Vu, 2010; Ibe *et al.*, 2021; Stanley *et al.*, 2024).

Abacheke, Mmahu, and Obokofia communities in Ohaji/Egbema are predominantly made up of farmers, and the soils of this area are fertile for farming (Apakama *et al.*, 2017). However, as a result of poor citation of auto-mechanic workshops in these areas, improper handling of wastes generated has led to soil degradation, thereby causing a remarkable decrease in the quality and quantity of harvested agricultural products (Eze *et al.*, 2024). The knowledge of the levels, sources, and possible interactions of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) with soil is important for monitoring the concentration levels in the environment. Several researchers have documented the presence of PAHs in soils polluted around auto-mechanic workshops (Obini *et al.*, 2013; Abhulimhen, 2016; Utibe *et al.*, 2020; Ibe *et al.*, 2021; Olusola *et al.*, 2024). However, there are no research reports on the PAHs concentrations and the physicochemical assessment of agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops in Ohaji/Egbema, Imo State: soil, health implications, and sustainability. Therefore, this study aims to fill the knowledge gap.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study

Ohaji/Egbema local government area is situated in Imo State and located geographically at longitude 6.8780° E and latitude 5.3138° N in the south-western part of Imo State. With approximately 958.010 km² area coverage, it has an estimated population of 800,904 people, with the capital located in Mmahu. It shares common boundaries with Oguta LGA in the north, Owerri in the east, and Ogba/Ndoni in Rivers State in the south-west (Apakama *et al.*, 2017).

Furthermore, located in a tropical valley, the soil is fertile for farming and human settlement. The study area has two seasons, namely, dry season and rainy season; with 2500–4000 mm mean annual rainfall and temperatures of 30 °C between April and December but rise to 34 °C between February and March (Eze *et al.*, 2021). This is as a result of the southwestern monsoon winds and the northeastern dry winds from the Atlantic Ocean and from across the Sahara Desert respectively (Apakama *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 1 Map showing the study area.

Collection of sample

Soil sampling was conducted within the selected communities, namely Abacheke (sample A), Mmahu (sample B), and Obokofia (sample C) communities, in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area, Imo State. Topsoil samples were collected at a

depth of 0-10 cm using a soil auger in ten (10) locations per community; subsequently, the samples collected for each community collectively formed a sample representative of the respective communities. The samples were then air-dried, sieved, and stored in pre-cleaned plastic cans. A control sample was

then taken from another community where there is no visible evidence of auto-mechanic activities or contamination of the soil. The soil samples and the control sample were taken to the laboratory for analysis. Additionally, the map was produced with the aid of a Garmin GPSMAP 76 using coordinates of the sampling points and the control sample. For this study, thirty soil samples and one control sample were collected.

Extraction of sample

Pre-extracted thimbles with 200 mL of dichloromethane (DCM) were used to soxhlet extract about 20 g of finely powdered soil samples for a minimum of 48 hrs. The accuracy of the methods were determined using surrogate standards (naphthalene-d8, acenaphthene-d10, phenanthrene-d10, chrysene-d12, and benzo[g,h,i]perylene-d12) before the extraction. To remove inorganic sulphur in the extract, activated copper was added. A glass column chromatography, packed with silica-alumina (2:1) chromatography was used to fractionate the concentrated extracts into aliphatic hydrocarbons and PAH fractions by successive elution with 20 mL *n*-hexane and 70 mL *n*-hexane/dichloromethane (7:3 v/v), respectively. The PAH fraction was further concentrated with a rotary evaporator at 30 °C

to approximately 1 mL, transferred to a 1.5 mL vial, and blown down to 0.5 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen (USEPA, 2010; Ibe *et al.*, 2021).

GC-MS analyses of sample

GC-MS analyses were performed on a Shimadzu Model 2010 GC-MS with an HP-5MS fused silica column (30 m × 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness) using a carrier gas (ultrapure helium) and 70 eV mass spectrometer electron impact mode. Injection of the samples was done in splitless mode at 100°C with a purge of 1 min after injection. The initial temperature was 60°C and heated to 200°C at 5 °C/min, then to 250°C at 2 °C/min, further heated to 280°C at 10°C/min (held for 20 min), and finally heated to 290°C at 10 °C/min (held for 5 min). The GC-retention times and mass spectrum with suitable reference standards were compared in order to identify the PAHs under study, while selective ion monitoring (SIM) mode was used to collect the data. Quantification was performed with a conventional internal calibration method (Ibe *et al.*, 2021; Olufunmilayo *et al.*, 2015).

Quality assurance and control

Analytical grade chemicals with high purity (98%) were used for this study. Suitable blanks (field, laboratory, spiked, and replicate)

and field samples were analyzed. The quantities of individual compounds were obtained using eight-point calibration curves and the internal calibration method. The average recoveries of the surrogate standards from all the blanks and the soil samples ranged from 65.5% to 99.6% and 70.5% to 100.5%, respectively. All the spikes have surrogate recoveries in the range of 75.0% – 120%, and the matrix also recorded surrogate recoveries in the range of 72.5% – 110.9% (Olufunmilayo *et al.*, 2015).

Soil pH

Soil pH was determined according to the method described by Radojevic and Bashkin (1999). 20g of air-dried soil samples, were weighed in triplicate and added into a 50 cm³ beaker, with the addition of 20 cm³ of distilled water, and the mixture was stirred occasionally using a glass rod for 30 minutes. Hanna digital pH meter, calibrated using a buffer solution of pH 7, was used to measure the pH. The pH measurement was taken by inserting the calibrated pH meter into the mixture.

Electrical conductivity (E.C)

The E.C analysis was carried out according to the APHA (1998) guidelines. Exactly 20g of air-dried soil samples was weighed in triplicate and added into a 250 cm³ beaker,

with the addition of 100 cm³ of distilled water. This gives a soil-to-distilled water ratio of 1:5. The mixture was then stirred for two (2) minutes and allowed to stand for five (5) minutes. The electrode cap of the E.C. meter was removed before switching on, then inserted into the solution and stirred. The display on the electrical conductivity meter was allowed to stabilize before readings were taken.

Temperature

The temperature of the soil samples were measured according to the methods described by APHA (1998). The thermometer probe was inserted into the soil, ensuring good contact. The temperature reading was allowed to stabilize for five minutes before the values were taken.

Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH)

The TPH of the soil sample was determined by the method of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) as described by Onianwa and Essein (1999) and Iwegbue *et al.*, 2007. 100 ml of methanol containing about 1.5 grams of KOH was used to reflux 50 grams of the soil samples for 2 hours and 30 minutes. The refluxed mixture was filtered, and the filtrate was extracted with two portions of 1.25 ml redistilled hexane. Both extracts were combined and evaporated to

about 0.5 ml and then purified in a silica column, eluted with n-hexane. In order to isolate the hydrocarbon oil, the eluate was evaporated, and then the hydrocarbon oil was weighed. Varying amounts of fresh automobile engine oil and repeated procedures for the analysis were carried out to obtain an average recovery of $90.7\pm 2.3\%$ for the study.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to present the data generated and analyzed using MS-Excel 2007.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Physicochemical parameters in the studied soil samples

Parameters	Sample A (Abacheke)	Sample B (Mmahu)	Sample C (Obokofia)	Control sample	Acceptable limit (USEPA 2010)
pH	4.83±0.37	3.99±0.24	4.45±0.13	7.98	6.5–8.5
Temp. (°C)	30.27±0.04	28.54±0.02	32.68±0.05	25.67	25 °C – 35 °C
Electrical conductivity $\mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$	230.57±41.32	269.13±38.94	295.31±26.01	98.34	400
Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (mg/kg)	947.61±35.08	1586.24±78.93	1246.85±89.23	196.18	50.00

pH

Mean pH values are within the range 3.99 ± 0.24 (Sample B) – 4.83 ± 0.37 (Sample A) in the soil samples. These values are significantly lower than the stipulated acceptable limit of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) (2010), indicating that the soil samples were acidic and are lower than the control sample of 7.98. The pH values obtained are lower than those obtained by Edori and Edori, 2012 but agrees with the studies carried out by Iwegbue *et al.*, 2008; Timothy *et al.*, 2021; and Amos *et al.*, 2023 in some agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops in Nigeria. Acidic soils will reduce the crop

yield and hence, treatment with slaked lime will neutralize the soil and improve crop production.

Temperature

The mean temperature (°C) values of the soil samples ranged from $28.54\pm 0.02^\circ\text{C}$ (Sample B) – $32.68\pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$ (Sample C). These values are within the stipulated acceptable limit of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). The mean temperature (°C) values of the studied soil samples are higher than the control sample 25.67°C .

Electrical Conductivity

Mean electrical conductivity values of the soil samples ranged from $230.57\pm 41.32 \mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$

(Sample A) – $295.31 \pm 26.01 \mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$ (Sample C). It can be seen that these values are significantly lower than the stipulated acceptable limit of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). The mean electrical conductivity values in the studied soil samples are greater than the control sample of 98.34. The high values were in agreement with the findings conducted in some agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops in Nigeria (Amos et al., 2023; Iwegbue *et al.*, 2008; Edori and Edori, 2012; Abhulimhen, 2016; Timothy *et al.*, 2021).

Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon

The mean total petroleum hydrocarbon values ranged from $947.61 \pm 35.08 \text{ mg/kg}$ (Sample A) – $1586.24 \pm 78.93 \text{ mg/kg}$ (Sample B) in the soil samples. It can be seen that these values are significantly higher than the stipulated acceptable limit of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). The mean total petroleum hydrocarbon values of the soil samples are also higher than the control sample, 196.18 mg/kg . The high values agree with the studies conducted by Abhulimhen, 2016; Lucky *et al.*, 2024. The high total petroleum hydrocarbon values were attributed to the anthropogenic values (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2008; Lucky *et al.*, 2024).

Table 2 PAH concentrations (mg/kg) in the studied soil samples

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon	Sample A (Abacheke)	Sample B (Mmahu)	Sample C (Obokofia)	Control
Naph	0.2831±0.01	0.3589±0.00	0.3071±0.01	0.0002
Acy	0.5196±0.01	0.3201±0.01	0.2905±0.00	0.0001
Ace	0.7067±0.00	0.7215±0.00	0.9047±0.01	0.0003
Fl	1.4874±0.02	1.2802±0.05	2.5086±0.01	0.0009
Phe	7.1577±0.05	7.5110±0.02	5.2337±0.00	0.0016
Ant	6.8432±0.03	7.1225±0.09	6.7044±0.03	0.0054
Flt	0.5818±0.01	0.8048±0.02	0.7308±0.01	0.0002
Pyr	0.9176±0.02	0.6586±0.00	0.5624±0.01	0.0005
*BaA	1.1396±0.01	0.5402±0.00	1.0453±0.02	0.0001

*Chr	0.1628±0.02	0.2997±0.01	0.3922±0.00	0.0002
*BbF	0.0121±0.01	0.0167±0.00	0.0148±0.01	0.0000
*BkF	0.0148±0.01	0.0130±0.00	0.0167±0.01	0.0000
*BaP	0.0111±0.00	0.0167±0.01	0.0185±0.02	0.0000
*DahA	0.0019±0.00	0.0018±0.01	0.0000±0.00	0.0000
BghiP	0.0000±0.00	0.0016±0.00	0.0019±0.01	0.0000
*Ind	0.0111±0.01	0.0019±0.00	0.0148±0.01	0.0000
Σ 16 PAHs	19.8505	19.6692	18.7464	0.0095
Σ LMW PAHs	10.1545	10.1917	9.2446	0.0031
Σ HMW PAHs	2.8528	2.355	2.7974	0.001

Naph-Naphthalene; Acy-Acenaphthylene; Ace-Acenaphthene; Fl-Flourene; Phe-Phenanthrene; Ant-Anthracene; Flt-Flouranthene; Pyr-Pyrene; *BaA-*Benz[a]anthracene; *Chr-*Chrysene; *BbF-*Benzo[b]flouranthene; *BkF-*Benzo[k]flouranthene; *BaP-*Benzo[a]pyrene; *DahA-*Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene; BghiP-*Benzo[g,h,i]perylene; *Ind-*Indenol[1.2.3-cd]pyrene

2–3 ring Low Molecular Weight (LMW) (From Nap to Ant).

4–6 ring High Molecular Weight (HMW) (From Flt – *Ind).

The results of PAHs in the soils of the studied samples, showed the variation of PAHs concentrations in mg/kg. Both the concentration of PAHs in the studied soil samples from the auto-mechanic workshops and the control site showed a remarkable difference. The total concentration (mg/kg) of the PAHs in the soil samples ranged from 18.7464 (Sample C) to 19.8505 (Sample A), greater than the 0.0095 mg/kg found in the control sample. The PAH values are higher in the studied soil samples than the concentration found in the control sample, this agrees with the studies reported by Abhulimhen, 2016; Eneji *et al.*, 2017;

Timothy *et al.*, 2023; Olusola *et al.*, 2024.

The high value of the mean PAHs concentration in the studied soil samples is an indication that the soil is contaminated and there is a high risk with human contact through the food chain (Obini *et al.*, 2013). This could be due to the fact that anthropogenic processes are responsible for the release of PAHs in these areas (Eneji *et al.*, 2017; Timothy *et al.*, 2021).

The control samples are within the range of 0.0000 mg/kg – 0.0054 mg/kg across PAHs. The control samples did not show any significant concentration level of PAHs when compared with studied soil samples from

auto-mechanic sites. This agrees with studies conducted by other researchers (Utibe *et al.*, 2020; Timothy *et al.*, 2021), which indicate that the soil is not contaminated.

The total concentrations (mg/kg) of 2–3 ring low molecular weight (LMW) PAHs from Nap to Ant at all sampling locations were above the 4–6 ring high molecular weight (HMW) PAHs from Flt – *Ind. This shows that there is a higher concentration of the 2–3 ring LMW PAHs than the 4–6 ring HMW PAHs in the soils within the study area. The finding is similar to the studies reported by Yuanxin *et al.*, 2020; Timothy *et al.*, 2023; and Eze *et al.*, 2024. However, the study's finding contradicts the finding conducted by Olusola *et al.*, 2024, in the soil around an automobile repair workshop in Nigeria, where the 4–6 ring HMW PAHs are more than the 2–3 ring LMW PAHs.

Mean Phenanthrene values of the soil samples ranged from 5.2337 ± 0.00 mg/kg (Sample C) – 7.5110 ± 0.02 mg/kg (Sample B), while the control sample showed 0.0016 mg/kg. Phenanthrene showed the highest concentration value of 7.5110 ± 0.02 mg/kg (Sample B), indicating that sample B is highly contaminated with Phenanthrene. This is followed by mean Anthracene values of the soil samples within the range of 6.7044 ± 0.03 mg/kg (Sample C) – 7.1225 ± 0.09 mg/kg

(Sample B), while the control sample showed 0.0054 mg/kg. Anthracene showed a higher concentration value of 7.5110 ± 0.02 mg/kg (Sample B). These findings are in agreement with studies conducted by Eze *et al.*, 2024. This is followed by Flourene, which showed a high value of 2.5086 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample C); mean values of the soil samples are within the range of 1.2802 ± 0.05 mg/kg (Sample B) – 2.5086 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample C), while the control sample showed 0.0009 mg/kg.

Others showed variable concentrations, such as mean Flouranthene values of the soil samples ranging from 0.5818 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.7308 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample C), while the control sample showed 0.0002 mg/kg. Mean Pyrene values are within the range of 0.5624 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample C) – 0.9176 ± 0.02 mg/kg (Sample A) in the soil samples, while the control sample showed 0.0005 mg/kg. Mean *Benz[a]anthracene values of the soil samples are within the range of 0.5402 ± 0.00 mg/kg (Sample B) – 1.1396 ± 0.01 mg/kg (Sample A), while the control sample showed 0.0001 mg/kg. Mean *Chrysene values are within the range of 0.1628 ± 0.02 mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.3922 ± 0.00 mg/kg (Sample C) in the soil samples, while the control sample showed 0.0002 mg/kg. Mean *Benzo[b]flouranthene values are within the range of

0.0121±0.01mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.0167±0.00 mg/kg (Sample B) in the soil samples, while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg. Mean *Benzo[k]flouranthene values of the soil samples are within the range of 0.0130±0.00 mg/kg (Sample B) – 0.0167±0.01mg/kg (Sample C), while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg. The mean *Benzo[a]pyrene of the soil sample values are within range of 0.0111±0.00 mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.0185±0.02 mg/kg (Sample C), while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg.

The mean *Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene values of the soil samples are within the range of 0.0000±0.00 mg/kg (Sample C) – 0.0019±0.00 mg/kg (Sample A), while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg. It can be seen that *Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene showed the least concentration value of 0.0000±0.00 mg/kg (Sample C), similar to the studies conducted by Eneji *et al.*, 2017. This shows that *Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene was not detected in sample C. Followed by *Benzo[g,h,i]perylene with mean values of the soil samples within the range of 0.0000±0.00 mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.0019±0.01 mg/kg (Sample C), while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg. *Benzo[g,h,i]perylene showed the least, 0.0000±0.00 mg/kg (Sample C) concentration

and was not detected in sample A. This is also followed by *Indenol[1.2.3-cd]pyrene with mean values within the range of 0.0019±0.00 mg/kg (Sample B) – 0.0148±0.01 mg/kg (Sample C) in the soil samples, while the control sample showed 0.0000 mg/kg. Naphthalene mean values are within the range of 0.2831±0.01mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.3589±0.00 mg/kg (Sample B) in the soil samples, while control sample showed 0.0002 mg/kg. The mean Acenaphthylene values of the soil samples are within the range of 0.2905±0.00 mg/kg (Sample C) – 0.5196±0.01 mg/kg (Sample A), while the control sample showed 0.0001 mg/kg. Acenaphthene mean values are within the range of 0.7067±0.00 mg/kg (Sample A) – 0.9047±0.01mg/kg (Sample C) in the soil samples, while the control sample showed 0.0003 mg/kg.

Conclusion

This study has revealed that agricultural soils around auto-mechanic workshops in Abacheke, Mmahu, and Obokofia in Ohaji/Egbema, are acidic (low pH) with high total petroleum hydrocarbon values, while electrical conductivity is lower than the recommended limit according to the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). It shows the variations of PAH

concentrations at all the locations in the study area; Phenanthrene, Anthracene and Fluorene were predominant in the three communities, while both *Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene and *Benzo[g,h,i]perylene showed the least. The 2–3 ring low molecular weight (LMW) PAHs in all sampling locations were higher than the 4–6 ring high molecular weight (HMW) PAHs. The high values of PAHs reported are an indication that the auto-mechanic workshop soils are highly contaminated, consequently affecting the soil quality negatively, reducing crop yield, thereby affecting food safety, security, and sustainability, and detrimental to human health. It is also a clear indication of anthropogenic activities around the study area. The findings recommend proper siting of auto-mechanic workshops far away from agricultural soils, education and adequate training for auto-mechanic workers, and subsequent collection and recycling of spent oils, which will in turn provide employment opportunities and provide revenue for the government.

Authors' contributions

NJO: writing- original draft preparation; VCE: visualization, conceptualization and methodology; CO: reviewing and supervision; AOE: editing and data curation; JNE:

investigation and software; KOE: methodology and validation; BNN: visualization.

Data availability

All data discussed in this study are available in the current tables and figures.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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